

“RIP English”: Race, class and ‘good English’ in India

Katy Highet

University of the West of Scotland

Correspondence

Katy Highet

Email: katy.highet@uws.ac.uk

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Abstract

This article explores how metapragmatic discourses on “good” and “bad” English in India are mobilized in ways that allow actors to negotiate their status as English speakers. Adopting an intersectional framework that highlights the relationality of colonial, racialized, and classed claims to authority, the article shows how the co-naturalization of language and race shapes assessments of competency and legitimacy and how this is mitigated through anti-Blackness and appeals to class status. These judgments of “good” and “bad” English work to reassert and undermine racialized authority over the language and position actors within an imagined, global stratified community of speakers. This ambivalent positioning not only helps actors negotiate relational legitimacy as English speakers but also works strategically to benefit certain speakers and reproduce colonial, class, and racial orders.

KEYWORDS

class, coloniality, English, India, race

At the hostel in Delhi where I stayed throughout my fieldwork, I befriended Dev, one of the front-of-house staff, who was born and raised in Goa but had moved from city to city since his late teens in search of stable employment. We spent many evenings chatting, and he appeared quite intrigued by my research, often provocatively yet playfully reminding me that he had no desire to speak like me—a white British woman. In particular, he told me, he was interested in why so many Indians, as he saw it, tried to “fake” a British or American accent. Having spent several years working at a call center for a British company where he had been required to undergo accent reduction training, Dev had grown tired of what he saw as pressure to speak like a “Westerner.” After leaving that job, he decided to never adopt that way of speaking again: “So I just stopped it long time, I’m like, OK I’m just gonna speak how I speak.” Dev certainly isn’t alone in adopting a stance of resistance to hegemonic Western

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standards; much has been written about the reappropriation and ownership of Englishes in postcolonial contexts. But Dev's position was often less stable than it appeared: his proclaimed resistance to British and American standards and his discursive reification and promotion of Indian English were shot right through with tensions.

When I returned to the hostel one evening after spending the day at the educational NGO that formed the basis of my ethnography, Dev seemed especially happy to see me. He beckoned me over to the desk, where he said he had something that he thought would be useful for my research. Earlier that day, he had come across a video on YouTube on how to speak with a British accent. (I often wondered, but never found out, whether he had sought this out himself or if he had chanced upon it.) "First," he said, "that guy was talking in an Indian accent so I was about to change [the video]." When I asked him why, he laughed, saying he thought it would be boring, until the speaker suddenly changed his accent and said, "See, I'm sure when you heard me talking you just thought I was whatever." As it turned out, while the bulk of the video delivers what the title promises—a lesson in "British" English pronunciation and expressions—the first three minutes are dedicated to a creative demonstration and explanation of linguistic discrimination. The presenter opens the video in strongly Indian-accented speech, switching after a minute or so to his habitual British accent to prove the point that his viewers would take him less seriously if he spoke in the former; indeed, this was precisely Dev's reaction. As I later discovered, the video was created by Anpu, a successful British YouTuber (86,900 subscribers) and filmmaker of "Tamil (South Indian) ethnicity" who uses his channel primarily to teach "British English and elocution." On his YouTube channel and web page, where he has popularized his hashtag #LoveYourIdentity, he describes his mission as "to help everyone around the world love their identity regardless of their race, gender, sexuality, or religion to live a better life." (<https://www.youtube.com/c/AnpuLondon/about>). The video Dev had shown me (<https://youtu.be/LAb7I9OWuR8>), titled "How to speak: BRITISH accent", has over 1.2 million views and sits alongside other equally successful videos such as "ADVICE: How not to sound FAKE British." Anpu's channel certainly appears well-meaning, and he does a good job of introducing his audience to a range of "British" accents (such as those of popular musicians Harry Styles or Stormzy). At the same time, however, he has built his profitable YouTube model upon standard language ideologies that jar with motivational messages about taking pride in one's identity. At the end of one video (<https://youtu.be/9bn9f3RSbHQ>) in which he "corrects" the pronunciation of common words ("espresso"), he signs off as follows:

When I was researching this video, um, I realized yeah there are, look, there are so many words aren't there which we're used to pronouncing in a certain way, but actually there's a proper pronunciation for them. So I want you to be honest with me: comment down in the comment section below how many you actually pronounced wrong. And yeah, remember, guys, *love* [makes L sign with right hand] *your* [points at the camera with index finger] *identity* [raises clenched fist], and I'll see you in the next one, cheerio.

Anpu's invocation of categories of identity ("race, gender, sexuality, or religion") to be celebrated reduces intersecting power relations that create racialized, colonial, and classed modalities of claims to authority and authenticity in the English language, and subsumes them under a discourse of diversity (Ahmed, 2012). His positive messages sit in tension with his mobilization of ideological frameworks that construct notions of "proper" English and "mistakes" and serve to uphold particular sociopolitical configurations. This tension is, I argue, a productive one, as it repackages English learning in the softer but ultimately superficial representation politics of #LoveYourIdentity (note the raised clenched fist he uses) while simultaneously allowing Anpu to profit through YouTube revenues from the hundreds of thousands of viewers who flock to

his channel in the hopes of improving their English and aligning themselves more closely to an imagined but socially powerful (Urciuoli, 2013) standard.

Videos like Anpu's, while seemingly progressive, draw on colonial and classed discourses of falling standards and language corruption (Milroy, 2001) that hierarchize language practices. Rooted in liberal multiculturalism (Kubota, 2015), #LoveYourIdentity makes claims to emancipatory goals and, on the surface, appears to be the antithesis of metalinguistic discourses that intentionally and rather cruelly disparage deviation. Perhaps the most striking example of this is the RIP English meme, in which photos of "humorous" English errors are circulated across social media, often accompanied by images of popular meme characters engaged in a funeral ritual for the *Oxford English Dictionary*. The examples are often taken from South Asia, and the memes, while not restricted to any one country, tend to circulate notably in this area: Google Trends data reveals that searches for "RIP English" between 2004 and 2022 have been most popular in Ireland, India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Nepal. This suggests that a great many of these memes are made *by* and *about* South Asians. While the RIP English meme has been documented elsewhere (Karjalainen, 2018; Spilioti, 2020), it circulates frequently across South Asian websites, forums, and social media, and certain posts have adapted the funeral meme to depict traditional Hindu funeral practices. The implication here is not only that English has been "killed" through "misuse" but that India is its place of death; Indians are guilty of its murder.

While the #LoveYourIdentity and RIP English discourses appear antithetical, they are articulated through and informed by the same logics and coexist along an ideological spectrum centered around the positing of standards and supposed deviations or decline. In this article, I explore how, through their metapragmatic discourse and entextualization of fragments of language as "good" or "bad" English, actors align themselves with an ideological framework that undermines and legitimizes certain English practices (and speakers) through co-articulated processes of racialization and class relations. In other words, rather than attending to discrete categories of identity (as in the #LoveYourIdentity discourse), I highlight the intersectionalities of these "mutually shaping" power relations (Hill Collins and Bilge, 2020) to demonstrate how authority over the English language is mediated through specific forms of structural racism (unmarked hegemonic whiteness and anti-Blackness) and social class (including types of schooling). This allows actors to negotiate their own status as English speakers within larger, stratified imagined communities layered upon the logics of coloniality, race, and class. This dynamic (dis)alignment, I will argue, is a profitable one as it allows actors to mitigate the explicit racial, colonial, and classed dimensions of standard language ideologies while nonetheless subscribing to and benefiting from the sociopolitical and ideological configurations that they reinscribe. Adopting an intersectional framework that highlights the relationality of colonial, racialized, and classed claims to authority, the article shows how the co-naturalization of language and race shapes assessments of competency and legitimacy and how this is mitigated through anti-Blackness and appeals to class status.

STANDARDS, MODELS, AND SPEAKERS

Both the RIP English meme and popular YouTube channels teaching "correct" English are anchored within particular discursive constructions of English and of language writ large. In order for it to be "killed," English must be reified as a standardized *thing* (Silverstein, 1996) susceptible to misuse. In Michael Silverstein's terms, the phenomenon of standardization is one through which the "institutional maintenance of certain valued linguistic practices—in theory, fixed—acquires an explicitly-recognized hegemony over the definition of the community's norm" (1996, 285), the effect of which is, as James Milroy notes, "the development of consciousness among speakers of a 'correct,' or canonical, form of language" (2001, 535)

and subordination of nonstandard forms as “deviant and non-compliant” (Cushing, 2021, 323). As many have argued, the language form that comes to serve as the standard model is anything but accidental, instead being “drawn primarily from the spoken language of the upper middle class” (Lippi-Green, 1997, 64), who in turn have a vested interest in maintaining its linguistic capital, partially through what Joseph Sung-Yul Park refers to as “interdiscursive chains of metapragmatic discourse such as etiquette manuals” (Park, 2021, 28). Since the dawn of language standardization, the maintenance of standards has been discursively packaged as a means to protect language from “corruption” or “decay” (Milroy, 2001, 550), which requires the ideological work of disaggregating natural developments of the language over time from “the deterioration of a tongue” (Marsh, 1865, 458, cited in Milroy, 2001, 550)—the categorization of which, as I show below, has less to do with linguistic features themselves and more with the context and producer of the utterance.

The notion of “corruptions” of English has heavily shaped debates over what are often referred to as New Englishes—varieties of English that have developed in postcolonial spaces such as Singapore, Nigeria, and India. Braj B. Kachru brought Indian English and other New Englishes to the attention of linguists in the latter half of the twentieth century and over time did a great deal to help establish Indian English within sociolinguistics as a socioculturally legitimate variety. What his “circles of English” framework (Kachru, 1985) suggested was not so much the development of new “standards” of English but the emergence of practices that diverged from an imagined “British” English and thus could be categorized as a separate but derivative variety.

While the World Englishes paradigm played an important role in the critical reassessment of global discourses of English, it has been critiqued on several accounts (Kubota, 2015; Saraceni, 2015; Tupas and Rubdy, 2015). Celebratory claims (Tupas and Rubdy, 2015) and premature declarations of decolonized Englishes across the world have been taken to task as examples of a liberal, “colorblind” approach (Kubota, 2015) that neglects the unshakable dominance of British and American standards in postcolonial contexts, and for their erasure of the continued hegemony of Standard English through global capitalism (O'Regan, 2021; see also O'Regan, 2014). For Ruanni Tupas, fields such as World Englishes have not paid sufficient attention to “the durable ideologies, practices and infrastructures of ELT,” analysis of which requires more than simply engaging in discourses of diversity of English language practices (“pluralizing, localizing, indigenizing”) and rather forces us to relocate them “within conditions of coloniality” (2022, 2). In his exploration of linguistic insecurity, Park draws on Labov's early work to argue that “speaker's recognition of an external standard” has self-illegitimizing effects (2021, 129), and demonstrates how colonial ideologies of nativeness intersect with neoliberalism to paint an imagined “Standard” English as both desirable and unobtainable—that is, desirable for its ostensible commodified market value yet unobtainable through colonial ideologies that construct Korean speakers as “bad” speakers of English (Park, 2021; see also Park, 2009). These old and new ideologies, far from being contradictory, converge to have the effect of “internalising the neoliberal hegemony of English grounded upon inequalities of race, ethnicity, and national identity as well as those of class” (Park, 2021, 128).

The critical sociolinguistic and linguistic anthropological approaches outlined above allow us to trace the historical and contemporary mobilization of “deficit colonial discourse(s)” (Tupas, 2022, 7) that reveal how notions of “native speakers” and standards are shaped not through objective linguistic judgment but rather through ideological processes of *speaker* categorization. As the concept of raciolinguistic ideologies (Flores and Rosa, 2015; Rosa and Flores, 2017) lays bare, evaluative judgments and interpretations of speakers' practices are mediated by processes and histories of racialization. In other words, racialized speakers are heard differently (as more or less competent or deviant) regardless of the “objective characteristics of their language use” (Flores and

Rosa, 2015, 151). Such assessments, Jonathan Rosa argues, are not limited to individualized speakers, but rather “invoke broader ideas about the (in)competence and (il)legitimacy of entire racialized groups” (2016, 163–64). These interpretations are alimeted by long-standing racist, colonial tropes of (in)competent populations that reinforce “essentializing relationships between language, ethnicity and personhood” (Carlan, 2018, 118; see also Bauman and Briggs, 2003; Nakassis and Annamalai, 2020). Not only are these discourses mobilized to delegitimize the speech practices of racialized actors, but they also serve moralizing agendas about falling language standards that are often aligned with (not very successfully) veiled racist tropes. As Catherine Tebaldi (2020a) shows in her work on mock youth French on French nationalist Twitter, the mobilization of colonial raciolinguistic discourses feeds into moralized anxieties about “social decline” (18) as the ostensible decline of the language is indexically linked to its use (or perhaps “abuse”) by “illiterate” racialized colonial subjects, which poses a threat not only to the language but also, by ideological extension, to the imagined white population itself. As such, discourses of falling standards are not only thoroughly moralizing endeavors but are also inextricable from their coarticulation with race and class. As Milroy (2001) argues, despite claims to the contrary from nineteenth-century scholars (and indeed many contemporary scholars), “there are no objective (non-ideological) criteria for distinguishing between ‘corruptions’ and ‘changes’” (550). Rather, such distinctions are shaped through ideological evaluations of the speaker.

This draws attention to how evaluative metalinguistic and metapragmatic stances on language use participate in interdiscursive, historical chains. One element of this is the process of (re)entextualization, through which “discourses are successively or simultaneously decontextualized and metadiscursively recontextualized,” thereby taking on a new reading (Blommaert, 2005, 47). The RIP English meme, for example, engages in entextualization as it removes texts from their original context of production (a Facebook post, a restaurant menu, etc.) and reinserts them in a new context that has its own history of production (the RIP English meme) that provides a particular lens through which to interpret the original text. As we will see, these entextualization moves allow a window into metalinguistic and metapragmatic discourse about “good” and “bad” English use. Metalanguage, as “people’s explicit, conscious, and articulated reflections about language—in other words, their talk about talk” (Thurlow, 2006, 669), is not restricted to the evaluation of and commentary on linguistic forms alone but rather includes their “social functions and the organization of social interaction through language” (Thurlow, 2006, 670). As such, metalinguistic discourse allows people to engage in a range of “personal identification work” and “social relationship work” (Jaworski, Coupland, and Galasiński, 2004), which in turn points us toward the ideological frames that mediate such metalinguistic talk. If all “talk about talk” falls under the umbrella of metalinguistic discourse, a focus on metapragmatic discourse—as “discourse about language use” (Park, 2021, 28)—allows us to make more explicit connections to how indexical meaning is renegotiated and reshaped as it circulates through interdiscursive chains and gets continually recontextualized and potentially re-signified at each moment of its uptake. Standard English, as Asif Agha writes, is a product of such interdiscursive chains of metapragmatic discourse, which were circulated through “publicly circulating document[s]” containing “explicit metasemiotic instruction in the management of such signs” (2007, 213), thereby “linking speech to social identity in substantial ways” (210), that is, to figures of personhood. Metapragmatic discourse thus serves as a “site for the generation and reproduction of language ideologies” (Park, 2021, 28; see also Woolard, 1998, 9) and for the continually renegotiated discursive linking of language use and social personae within particular social conditions; a focus on metapragmatic discourse, therefore, allows us to access moments of intersubjective negotiation in which “participants in interaction present themselves as particular kinds of subjects” (Park, 2021, 129).

The data explored in this article comes not from etiquette guides but from a series of interactions in which examples of "good" and "bad" English are taken up, re-entextualized, and accompanied by a metapragmatic discourse that provides implicit and explicit guidance on how one should or shouldn't speak. As I will argue, this metalinguistic and metapragmatic discourse not only draws from and reinforces colonial and raciolinguistic ideologies; it also allows participants to negotiate their own positioning in an inter- and intra-national imagined community of speakers stratified along the lines of race, coloniality, and class. As we will see, these stance-taking moves are not only about positioning and signaling one's identity; they can also become profitable personae to adopt.

COLONIAL AND CLASSED CONTOURS OF ENGLISH IN INDIA

In the ethnographic context that I draw upon, the production and co-naturalization of language, ethnicity, and personhood can be traced back, in part, to technologies of population management, regulation, and knowledge production (Duchêne and Humbert, 2018) that were embedded within colonial governmentality (Foucault, 1991). This includes the introduction of a census but also extends to linguistic scholarship such as the Linguistic Survey of India (LSI) (1903–1928), undertaken by George Abraham Grierson. In her examination of the LSI, Hannah Carlan demonstrates how the objectification of language "as a natural object" led to "essentialized portraits of 'weak' and 'strong' languages," characteristics that were then transferred to its speakers' "intellectual capacities" (2018, 101). These raciolinguistic ideologies also informed colonial debates over the medium of education for Indians (see, e.g., Annamalai, 2005; Evans, 2002; Pennycook, 1998) in which advocates of English education drew on discourses of civilization and enlightenment and the construction of the inherently "superior" language of English as a means to access science, modernization, and "the benefits of European knowledge" (Annamalai, 2005; Pennycook, 1998, 75). English thus became a "gift" to be bestowed upon a select few of the local population, thereby producing and demarcating the newly emerged middle class, as those with the means and aspiration for mobility within the colonial structure came to "rely on [colonial] education as a means of achieving access to employment and economic power" (Fernandes, 2006, 4). This new social group—the colonial Indian middle class, distinguished primarily by its English education—thus sat in "an uneasy relationship both with traditional elites as well as with other less privileged segments of the middle classes, particularly the vernacular, lower middle classes" as "new forms of distinctions" emerged (Fernandes, 2006, 5). As these distinctions were consolidated throughout the nineteenth century, this newly formed group developed a vested interest in the maintenance and reproduction of colonial categories, processes, and hierarchies as their own socioeconomic positions and cultural capital were dependent upon them.

Post-independence, English education continued as a stronghold of a select few until the neoliberal restructuring of the economy in the early 1990s, at which time the number of (private) institutions offering English training began to surge. This, of course, is not without conflict, as debates over language provision sit within conflicting imaginaries of the modern Indian nation (Hall, 2019)—particularly in the current political moment of increasing Hindu nationalism and its fraught relationship with the English language (LaDousa, 2014). While access to English has certainly increased, the acquisition of English today remains embedded in the formation of class boundaries, and access to prestige varieties remains financially impossible for the vast majority of middle-class aspirants. Despite the fractured, unequally valued, and heterogeneous nature of various Indian English practices (Ramanathan, 2015)—which are often linked to bifurcated types of schooling (vernacular-medium versus English-medium;

government schools versus private or “convent” schools), English continues to be reified and objectified as a desirable object that can provide its speakers with cultural capital, prestige, and pride (Proctor, 2015). The association of English with a particular middle-classness is so potent (Highet and Del Percio, 2021a, 2021b) that the inability to command the language comes to be perceived as the only obstacle to social mobility: “the reason for their social backwardness” (Roy, 2015, 525). While many have shown this promise to be somewhat elusive and misleading (Duchêne and Daveluy, 2015; Highet, 2022; Tabiola and Lorente, 2017), the supply of and demand for English education and training centers have boomed over the last few decades.

In the analysis that follows, I draw first on data from one of these centers, which was a primary focus of my ethnographic work (2018–2019). This NGO, with several hundred branches across North India, provides an English and employability program free of cost to young adults, who attend daily classes for one year. For the most part, the students who attend the NGO are or have been enrolled in Hindi-medium government schools (i.e., state education) and would otherwise be unable to afford English education. The first interaction that I explore below is taken from one of the frequent training sessions that are provided for facilitators (teachers) at the beginning of their training and throughout their careers in the NGO. Specifically, I draw on one interaction in which a series of videos is entextualized by the trainer, who, through his metalinguistic and metapragmatic discourse, sketches out the contours of “good” or “desirable” English. To draw out the interdiscursive chains that transcend the particular moment and boundaries of the NGO, in the second analysis, I turn to another instance of metapragmatic discourse and metalinguistic commentary of “good” and “bad” English, this time through a video from a popular YouTuber, whom I first came across in conversation with Indian staff and guests at my hostel in Delhi in 2018. In this video, released three years after I was introduced to his channel, we see the entextualization of a viral video from the Ghanaian comedian Akrobeto. Through the juxtaposition of these seemingly disparate moments, I show how the NGO trainer’s metadiscursive commentary draws on and recirculates the same logics that underpin the YouTuber’s explicit mobilization of RIP English and its intersectional layering of class and race in the hierarchization of English practices.

GOOD, BETTER, BEST ENGLISHES

The facilitators at the NGO came from a variety of backgrounds. In the branch where I spent the most time, the two facilitators had both previously been students at the NGO, and upon completing the course—at which they had excelled—they had been invited to undergo in-house training to become facilitators. This, I soon learned, was quite a common trajectory, and many of the facilitators were former students of the NGO. Aside from the initial training, facilitators regularly attended training days at the headquarters in Delhi led by trainers employed by the NGO, which was an opportunity to develop their teaching skills, improve their language accuracy, and discuss issues with other facilitators and senior trainers. From my interactions with the training team, I learned that, in contrast with the majority of the facilitators, for the most part the training team had been educated in English-medium (with some exceptions) and were university graduates.

In one of the training days I observed, which was made up of relatively new facilitators, I was pleasantly surprised to hear the senior trainer encourage the trainees to be proud of their “Indian” English. My surprise emanated in part from my experiences in the NGO as well as in other Indian schools where I, through my whiteness and Britishness, was often interpellated as a “model” to emulate. Much like I had heard from Dev, the trainer insisted several times that students should not seek to copy the British or American accent as there was

nothing wrong with speaking like an Indian (#LoveYourIdentity). To make his point, he had lined up a selection of videos to show to the student-facilitators, reminding them that in the morning he had promised to show them a video of Indians speaking good English. The first video—a clip of an Indian stand-up comedian performing at an event in Delhi—was spoken in what would largely be recognized as “standard” grammar with a recognizably Indian accent, one that, in my experience, indexed an English-medium education. The video, the trainer explained, had been chosen to show students that good English and an Indian accent were not incompatible, and he commended the comic for a “pretty good accent” and for being “understandable.”

The evaluation of the comic's English is tied to comprehensibility and intelligibility, which invokes an outward positioning that frames the assessment of “good” English in India as dependent on the judgment of interlocutors, that is, the judgment of those whom speakers must make themselves intelligible *for* (Rajagopalan, 2010). The students themselves are directly interpellated by this question of intelligibility as the trainer tells them that they will struggle to be understood if they use their (vernacular-medium, non-private) school accents. This was not to say that there was anything *wrong* with the English they had acquired from their (predominantly government) schools, he continued, but this would be intelligible only to Indians, not foreigners. Thus, within what on the surface appears to be a nonjudgmental means to categorize their speech practices and a way to displace the notion of the native speaker by seemingly granting legitimacy to Indian English speakers, we see that the notion of intelligibility continues to place Indian practices of English within a hierarchy of Englishes, with the students' (vernacular-medium, non-private) school English ranking lowest. As Ryuko Kubota (2015) writes, this places the responsibility of being understood on the (often racialized) speaker, who must modify their own practices to suit the expectations of the listening subject. This has material consequences: the emergence of industries such as accent-training—common especially in call centers (Chand, 2009; Ramjattan, 2022)—allows legitimized speakers to capitalize on their “intelligibility,” which reinforces their colonial and class-based authority over the language while masking the ideological superiority of their practices with the apparently neutral judgment criterion of intelligibility. Despite attempts to celebrate Indian English, the mobilization of intelligibility reinforces this ideological framework. Of course, this may also be a strategic choice that emerges from familiarity with the demands of global English language exams that stipulate intelligibility as a key part of the rubric, exams that many of these students may hope to take in the future. Even so, mobilizing intelligibility reinscribes the hierarchy of speech practices that relegates the students' “school English”—a couched reference to class, given that the majority of facilitators attended government schools—to a subordinate position.

Following the video of the stand-up comedian, the second clip showed an Indian with what was described as a “much better” accent. This time, we were presented with an extract from an interview on the Canadian news channel CBC with the actor Priyanka Chopra Jonas, famed for her work in Bollywood and Hollywood films as well as on American television series. Prior to becoming a celebrity, Chopra Jonas had attended several prestigious English-medium schools in India before moving to the United States for three years when she was a teenager. Her speech reflects this international trajectory because although she retains Indian-accented speech, she also bears the traces of her time spent in North America, particularly in the context of her being interviewed by a Canadian reporter for a Canadian news channel, where a certain degree of linguistic alignment with her interlocutor and imagined audience would not be unusual. In any case, while Chopra Jonas's speech is recognizable as Indian, she is both structurally and phonologically much closer to an imagined standard North American English than the comedian in the first clip. “See how her accent is better?” the trainer asked. The message is clear: a little Indianness is fine, but the less, the better.

The metalinguistic commentary on the two first video clips indicates a contradictory stance toward the hierarchization of practices of English. Much as with Anpu's #LoveYourIdentity message, there is a tension between, on the one hand, the insistence that students should be proud of Indian English and, on the other, a metapragmatic discourse that discourages students from using their “school” accents for fear they will be unintelligible. This allows for a reassertion of the commenter's own authority—as an English-medium-educated Indian—over the language, and at the same time discursively locates the students and their “school” practices as occupying an inferior position within a stratified global community of speakers.

Alongside the more overt dimensions of class relations, in the first two videos the mediating influence of racialization in processes of linguistic authority remains somewhat implicit and subsumed within colonial dynamics. In the third video, however, the co-naturalization of race and language, and how this, in turn, shapes assessments of competence and legitimacy, became more explicit. As the third clip in what was entextualized as instances of increasingly better English, the implication was that this one was the winner. It was a clip of Hasan Minhaj, an American stand-up comedian. Minhaj, who self-describes as an Indian American Muslim, was born and raised in California after his parents migrated from India. In this clip, Minhaj speaks in standardized, California-accented North American English, with no traces (here at least) of what Shalini Shankar (2008) calls Desi Accented English or FOB (fresh off the boat) styles. By presenting this—a speaker using standard North American English—as an example of the “best” English, the training clip shows not only a contradiction of earlier comments about not needing to emulate British or American norms but also the mobilization of raciolinguistic ideologies (Rosa and Flores, 2017). The aim of this exercise, as I understood it, was not simply to show and evaluate a range of different practices of English; rather, it was explicitly framed as an example of *Indians* speaking “good” English. It would not have made sense—nor would it have suited the exercise's objective—to share a clip of a white British or American speaker. And yet, by sharing this clip of Minhaj speaking a language that he was both educated and socialized in through his upbringing in the United States, it is suggested that there is something essentially different about white and Indian speakers of English, regardless of how they acquired the language. Whether the trainer knew that Minhaj is American is beside the point—Minhaj's practices are interpreted first and foremost through his racialization as Indian. Minhaj's Americanness is thus erased, but so too is the Americanness of his speech, which, through its being labeled as simply “good” English, obscures global processes that construct certain variants (and speakers) as linguistically superior.

The re-entextualization of this clip among a series of good, better, and best English reinforces a hierarchy of not only speech practices (with the ultimate goal being one that is practically unobtainable) but also speakers, as it carries the implication that racialized Indians—wherever they grow up—are not authentic speakers of the language in the same way as white speakers. English is associated not only with a nation-state but with a people who bear “particular racial, ethnic, or other background attributes stereotypically understood to be essentialized markers of membership in a specific group” (Park and Wee, 2009, 396). Although the intentions behind inclusion of the Minhaj clip were likely well-meaning—much as they were for the #LoveYourIdentity discourse—this metapragmatic discourse draws on a construction of authentic English speakers as white, not Indian. Celebrating this as an achievement—that is, as something to be remarked upon—for an American man racialized as Indian implicitly reinforces the *unmarked* whiteness of Standard English, thereby undermining the trainer's own claims to authority as an Indian. Authority is reasserted, however, through his alignment with the figure of the language arbiter, which places him in a relationship of superiority with the students, a superiority that is articulated through class relations. As we will see, this naturalization of race and language, and their coarticulation with class, work in similar albeit more explicit ways to inform wider, linked discourses of “bad” English.

"THIS AFRICAN REPORTER CAN'T READ": RACE, COMPETENCY, AND AUTHORITY

RawKnee is a popular YouTuber, often described as a "roaster" and a gamer, from Mumbai. Since his first video in 2015, he has become an increasingly influential name in the (Indian) e-sports world, and in 2020 he was featured on a list of the 300 Most Influential People in Asia (curated by journalist and entrepreneur Kiran Rai and commissioned by the New York Press News Agency) (Assundani, 2020). He boasts several million subscribers across his four YouTube channels: over 3.6 million and 1.81 million for his two most popular channels. Today he is better known for his gaming channel, where he livestreams himself playing and commenting on video games, but his second most popular channel, a comedy channel, was where he first launched his online career. His first video, published in 2015 and titled "Top 10 R.I.P English #1," (<https://youtu.be/dqjnPhBH3bs>) became part of a series of more than 20 videos to date that are titled or tagged with "RIP English." Of the 169 videos on *The RawKnee Show*, the RIP English series sits alongside a range of other comedy videos in which he "roasts" (i.e., ridicules) and reacts to a range of TikTok videos, viral content, memes, TV shows, and pop culture. As Sahana Udupa (2018) writes, insult comedy, modeled on the roast comedy that emerged in the United States, has heavily influenced online participation practices in India—particularly in online political discourse—and it sits within wider online practices of trolling and abuse that, she notes, are particularly heightened for women. As a form of insult comedy, the RIP English videos are a popular feature of the channel, with all the newer videos (since 2017) having between 1 million and 1.5 million views. Each video follows more or less the same format, in which RawKnee presents and comments upon examples of English "fails." The examples—almost exclusively from South Asia—are usually photos or screenshots of nonstandard spelling or grammar (e.g., "bed shits for sale"; "you are look like really beauty woman") on Facebook posts, restaurant menus, or shop advertisements, although in the later videos he includes increasingly more video clips (e.g., a contestant on *Bangladeshi Idol*), and he often features examples submitted by his fans. His reactions are rather predictable—he laughs out loud, expresses exasperation through a double face-palm, claps his hands in faux congratulation with a thick layer of sarcasm ("wah bhai wah"), and mocks speakers' English by mimicking their utterances in heavily accented, highly stylized nonstandard English.

Over the six years that RawKnee has been posting these videos, their tone has somewhat shifted. In the first few, he includes his own disparaging comments below the video, such as "Today we take a look at TOP 10 times English was murdered brutally by stupid people." Since 2017, however, as his online persona has developed, he has begun to include written disclaimers:

I DONT (sic) MEAN TO INSULT ANYONE FOR NOT BEING FLUENT IN ENGLISH. It is to target the stupid mindset of Indians that measure your litaracy (sic) with your control over the English language which makes a lot of people who aren't fluent, feel embarrassed. NEVER BE EMBARASSED (sic) IF YOU CAN'T SPEAK A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. BE PROUD OF YOUR NATIONAL LANGUAGE. (<https://youtu.be/kaDI0I4dFYk>)

This shift in tone is accompanied by a marked improvement in the production quality of his videos. His current streamer aesthetic, complete with background lighting, professional external microphone, and gaming headset, is a far cry from the poorly lit, low-sound-quality videos with minimal edits that he first produced in 2015. Undoubtedly this increase in production quality has something to do with the monetization of his channel (many of his videos now include paid promotion for cryptocurrency), which began in 2017 as his followers began to increase

exponentially. However, as several of his followers have pointed out, the production quality is not the only thing that has been transformed over the years. In 2017—around the time when his site became lucrative—there was a noticeable shift in RawKnee's language practices. In the first few RIP English videos (2015), RawKnee speaks entirely in (standard) English. By 2017, as his online persona started to develop, he had switched predominantly to Hindi, with occasional use of English, Bengali, and Marathi—so much so that many of his newer followers claim to be surprised to learn that RawKnee is a highly competent English speaker.

In December 2021, RawKnee released a new video called “THIS AFRICAN REPORTER CAN'T READ” (over half a million views at the time of writing) (<https://youtu.be/k-vC1MQYb9M>). While it was not explicitly titled “RIP English,” RawKnee includes the hashtag #ripenglish in the video description and in the introduction, thereby entextualizing the video as part of this genre and inviting the audience to interpret what follows as an instantiation of bad English. Indeed, many of his fans appear to have interpreted it as such, with some comments describing it as the best RIP English video so far. In the video we see RawKnee follow his usual format of introducing a viral clip and commenting on it. The clip in question—the original of which has nearly 4.5 million views—shows Ghanaian entertainer Akrobeto reading the results of European football leagues in a UTV news studio. Beginning with the English Premier League and continuing through the Italian and German leagues, the presenter appears to struggle with the pronunciation of the team names, with his attempts getting increasingly far from the standardized pronunciation as the clip goes on, prompting RawKnee to claim, laughing, that “*Is point pe uncle sirf aavaaj hi nikaal raha hai. Uncle abhi kuch kar nahi raha hai, sirf aavaaj nikaal raha hai* (At this point Uncle's just making sounds. He's not doing anything else, just making sounds).” RawKnee appears highly amused throughout the video, at one point laughing so hard he almost spits out the water he is drinking and knocks his bottle cap to the floor, and he frequently mocks the reporter's putative errors in pronunciation by mimicking them in a highly stylized way.

In this sense, RawKnee's video is not too dissimilar from the others in the series. What is different this time, however, is that RawKnee appears not to have understood that the original video by Akrobeto—a comedian—is intentionally stylized for comedic purposes. Stating that “Uncle's job is to appear on a TV channel and report news about sports,” RawKnee appears to have interpreted Akrobeto's video as an example of a genuinely incompetent news reporter, rather than as a sketch made by a comedian. In other words, Akrobeto's stylization—his “exaggerated representations of languages, dialects, and styles” beyond his habitual repertoire (Rampton, 2009, 149)—is not interpreted by RawKnee through a performance frame. Stylization, as Ben Rampton writes, emerges from a perceived “disjuncture” between speaker and voice that “violates co-occurrence expectations,” (2009, 152) thus shifting the interpretative frame. Here, however, RawKnee does not appear to recognize the “disjuncture” that stylization relies upon to be interpreted as such.

This misrecognition of the stylized performance of Akrobeto's sketch, I argue, is mediated by raciolinguistic ideologies informed by Akrobeto's racialization as a Black African (evident, for example, in the title “THIS AFRICAN REPORTER CAN'T READ”). The assumption of incompetence and illiteracy (rather than parodic performance) is fueled by racialized colonial tropes around Blackness and Africanness. Colonial discourses constructed the colonized as savages in need of civilizing and education, which was to be enacted through the colonial language and its attendant enlightening knowledge. Through the explicit racialization of Akrobeto, we see RawKnee mobilize not only wider colonial tropes but also specific tropes of Black colonial subjects as, in Frantz Fanon's words, “savages, morons, and illiterates” (2008, 96). In her analysis of the African linguistic figure still in circulation in France today, Cécile Vigouroux describes the intermeshing of racial and linguistic ideologies that construct Africans as “incompetent speakers of French” (2017, 7). While the colonial language in question here is English, the underlying trope of (Black) Africans as “putatively

inarticulate and primitive" (Vigouroux, 2017, 5) remains the dominant lens through which Akrobeto's stylization is (mis)interpreted. Regardless of the fact that what Akrobeto is (mis)pronouncing are actually the names of not only English football teams but also Italian and German teams—and therefore their (mis)pronunciation does not necessarily indicate a lack of competency in speaking English—his performance is interpreted through a raciolinguistic lens that allows it to be recognized as an instantiation of RIP English. In other words, through its re-entextualization, it serves to perpetuate the construction of (Black) colonial subjects as illiterate. Situating this within a raciolinguistic framework, we can see how RawKnee, although himself racialized as non-white, adopts a white listening subject position (Flores and Rosa, 2015; see also Inoue, 2006).

RawKnee's commentary on Akrobeto's sketch not only reproduces anti-Black racist and colonial tropes (under the guise of roasting), but it also works to both reassert and undermine his own racialized authority over the language by participating in "racialized hierarchies of personhood" (Rosa, 2016, 165) that situate Indians and Black Africans (and by implicit extension, whiteness) in a stratified relationship. At the beginning of the video, RawKnee exaggeratedly performs his own struggle with Akrobeto's name, stuttering over the first two syllables, before claiming he has forgotten the name, instructing someone off screen to pass him the script, and asking, "*Bhai itna difficult naam kyun hai uncle ka?* (Bro, why is Uncle's name so difficult?)." Here, RawKnee's stumbling is not framed as proof of incompetence in the same way as Akrobeto's; at fault is not RawKnee's (stylized) incompetency but rather Akrobeto's unpronounceable name. Once again, RawKnee's jibe draws its humor from its mobilization of colonial tropes that construct non-European names (here, African names) as foreign and difficult and thus uphold Eurocentric racial hierarchies centered around whiteness (Sium, 2011). The irony here, of course, is that this trope equally serves to marginalize South Asians who encounter similar microaggressions in the United States and Europe (Kohli and Solórzano, 2012).

Through his mobilization of anti-Black racist tropes for comedic effect, RawKnee asserts his own authority and competence and undermines that of Akrobeto. There are, however, important instances of shifting stance alignment throughout the video as RawKnee renegotiates his relationality to Akrobeto and to the wider English-speaking world or, more specifically, to an imagined ultimate authority over English (implicitly coded as hailing from England). For example, when Akrobeto struggles with the team name "Wolverhampton Wanderers," RawKnee claims, "*Bhai, yeh toh mujhe padhna nai aa raha hai* (Bro, I don't even know how to read this)," before reading it with a standard pronunciation. On the one hand, by admitting his own inability he undermines his own authority, and one might be tempted to interpret this as an act of humility. Yet on the other hand, RawKnee's attempts at modesty, when put in the context of the transformations of his channel over the last seven years, appear disingenuous, even patronizing, particularly given that he proves himself entirely capable of pronouncing the team's name in a standardized way. His performative self-deprecation here stands in stark contrast with the self-assured persona of his earlier videos—by far the least popular, with views in the thousands rather than the millions—which were, as mentioned, delivered entirely in (standard) English. RawKnee's switch from English to Hindi, whether or not it was strategic (Jaworski, Coupland, and Galasiński, 2004) or conscious (Bakhtin, 1981), has allowed him to ingratiate himself with a much wider audience—perhaps, even, to appeal to increasing nationalist sentiment (see, for example, his references to "national language" and the framing of English as a "foreign" language in his written disclaimer). This developed persona has proven to be very lucrative—he is currently sponsored by a Bitcoin company—but it is one that requires careful curation. Because he is a highly competent speaker of English, his mocking of English errors risks appearing arrogant and elitist. But through the Hindi-speaking persona that he has developed, who mixes RIP English jokes with moments of apparent modesty, declarations of his own incompetence, and written disclaimers, he is

able to avoid alienating his Hindi-speaking audience, many of whom are likely to struggle with their own anxieties around speaking English. Part of the popularity of RawKnee's show, I suggest, lies in how it allows his viewers to inhabit a relational superiority by mocking the mistakes of others—here, Africans and the lower classes in South Asia—and allowing them to identify with the figure of the mocker, thereby feeling secure that they, too, are in on the joke, that they are not the ones being laughed at.

RawKnee's humor thus has important subject-positioning effects. Outlining humor as an important feature of racism, Jane Hill's (1998, 2005) work on Mock Spanish demonstrates the dual indexicality of mock language practices that work to elevate whiteness as they directly index the humor or other positive qualities of the speaker and indirectly conjure up images of a recognizable, racialized figure that circulates in intertextual series. This figure is essential for the humor to be interpreted and understood, but it also allows such practices to be deniable as forms of racism. Of course, mock language practices can also be overtly racist: Tebaldi (2020b) shows how the far right use mock speech to position themselves as distinct from migrants. But they also use mock speech to engage in identity construction and the reassertion of whiteness by positioning themselves against the global elite, meaning that their mock language is used to both “demonize” and “satirize” a range of targets who are perceived as more or less powerful. While the examples Tebaldi offers clearly demonstrate the demarcation of difference through the use of mock language, Elaine W. Chun's work draws attention to the ambiguity of mock language, particularly in cases where the mocking is enacted by members of the group. On the one hand, members who can “authenticate” their belonging are licensed to mock the features of their own community (Chun, 2004). On the other hand, community membership is “hardly categorically definable” (18), and speakers can be “understood by different observers and at different times as variously positioned in relation to the particular community in question” (19). This is what appears to underwrite the tension that RawKnee has to carefully navigate as he attempts to authenticate his membership to the community whose language practices he is mocking by aligning himself increasingly with Hindi and distancing himself from the figure of the arrogant, English-speaking elite. This is not only a question of increasing his follower count: this tension sits within a background of polemical conflict that undergirds discussions of language, modernity, and nationalism in the postcolonial Indian state. Although RawKnee doesn't engage in explicitly mocking the elite (as in, e.g., Reyes, 2017), the figures of both colonial and postcolonial elites are implicit in his videos, as well as in the NGO trainer's discourse. They both position themselves in opposition to this figure through the discursive rejection of British and American norms (the trainer) or the gradual phasing out of English entirely (RawKnee); at the same time, they distance themselves from the figure of the lower-class, racialized speaker through mocking (RawKnee) or delegitimizing (trainer) their language practices. Through this, we see both a reassertion and a demarcation of an implicitly moralized middle-classness that emerges in contrast with “more and less desirable forms” (Reyes, 2017, 228) of Indianness.

DISCUSSION

I have outlined the intersecting racial, colonial, and class logics that inform and in turn are informed by evaluative metalinguistic and metapragmatic discourses of “good” and “bad” English language practices in India. Much like historical processes of language standardization that have been integral to nation-state building (Silverstein, 1996, 286; see also Bauman and Briggs, 2003), these standard language discourses have exclusionary effects, drawing boundaries around what—and by extension *who*—is welcome in the demarcated space. Through their metapragmatic discourse, the actors in this article engage in dynamic negotiation of their own positioning with regard to the imagined standard, through which, as

I have shown, they both undermine and reassert their own classed and racialized authority over the language. One way they do this is by appealing to the figure of the corrector and thus occupying "the role of linguistic gatekeeper instead of the linguistically gate-kept" (Babcock, 2022, 333). As an extension of the role of gatekeeper, the RIP English meme and the rather cruel mocking that it entails—which, as Priti Sandhu (2015) has demonstrated, is hardly restricted to online discourse—relegates the object of the joke to a "stigmatized, subordinate position" (222). This locates the actors relationally, as their positioning depends upon the discursive power to categorize others' practices. While such moves allow English-medium-educated Indians to negotiate their positionality vis-à-vis lower-class Indians and differently racialized speakers and thus to fight for their position in a global hierarchy of speakers and speech practices, to do so they must subscribe to and reinscribe logics of race and class—a compromise, of sorts, that loosens the ideological belt just enough to extend recognition to certain racialized, upper middle-class speakers while ensuring the reproduction of the underlying stratifying structures.

On the one hand, the discursive superiority granted to those who engage in boundary-making practices (by simply stating what counts as "good" English, or by explicitly mocking nonstandard English) can partially explain the popularity of such memes and the discourses that infuse them. On the other hand, however, there are risks involved when occupying elitist, patronizing, and arrogant positions. This elitist positioning, as we have seen, can be to some extent mitigated by appealing to liberal discourses of diversity and representational politics (#LoveYourIdentity) or by instructing viewers to "BE PROUD" of their national language. In the context of highly contested debates over the imagination of the Indian nation (Hall, 2019), these moves allow actors to distance themselves from the figure of the English-speaking, Western-facing (post)colonial elite and appeal to popular anti-English nationalist discourses (see, for example, the near erasure of English from the BJP's 2020 National Education Policy (LaDousa, Davis, and Choksi, 2022; LaDousa and Davis, 2022), or recent appeals from the home minister Amit Shah to replace English with Hindi as the country's lingua franca, all under the guise of progressive politics). Yet, much like the #LoveYourIdentity discourse demonstrated, actors do so while reaping the benefits of their proximity to English, profiting from the anxieties they ostensibly seek to dispel and reinscribing the colonial, racial, and class logics that they are both constrained and enabled by. Their dynamic positioning—how they both reassert and undermine their racialized and classed authority over the language—is thus a profitable one. It is profitable quite literally for the likes of RawKnee; but for the NGO, it is beneficial in that—whether intentionally or not—it affords a certain level of protection from the increasingly concerning rise of far-right Hindu nationalism in order to avoid, to the extent possible when engaging in English teaching, being targeted as anti-national and thus endangering the future of the NGO. I hasten to add here that I am certainly not accusing the trainer nor the NGO of pandering to nationalist sentiment, nor is it my intention to single this person out—I could have chosen one of many such interactions from my data. What I do seek to do, however, is draw attention to how putatively apolitical organizations are situated within—and participate in—wider ideological frameworks that are often in conflict as various political and ideological standpoints compete for hegemony.

Adopting an intersectional lens on the circulation of Standard English discourses, then, allows for an account of power relations not as discrete domains but as working together to dynamically, interactively mediate the (de)legitimization of Englishes and English speakers. While the politics of English in India are often explored through aspects of colonial and class relations, incorporating a raciolinguistic perspective allows us to tease out the modalities through which colonial relations are upheld. That is, it provides an account of how whiteness continues to shape relations *between* (post)colonial subjects beyond the colonizer–colonized encounter and of how racial orders can be subscribed to by actors who both benefit from and are harmed by them. But, as the examples in this article have shown, this proximity to whiteness that grants

discursive authority over English through alignment with gate-keeping practices of standardization is inextricable from how these same practices are co-articulated through class relations and the negotiation of middle-classness. This coarticulation allows actors to strategically position themselves (i.e., as relationally authoritative yet not elitist; as one of the people yet superior) and thus mitigate accusations of being classist, racist, or anti-national.

What this article has not been able to account for is how these positioning practices are further affected by gender (see Highet, 2022) or caste. This raises questions about the extent to which a raciolinguistic perspective could be a productive lens through which to explore the effects of caste relations (for further discussion, see Chandras, this issue), particularly given numerous scholars' warnings about the dangers of conflating race with caste (Banerjee-Dube, 2014). What should be noted, however, is how these multitudes of intersecting identities are certainly not overlooked by the actors in this article—this is not a case of their misrecognizing race, class, gender, and so on as mediating factors. Rather, what this shows is how intersectionality gets taken up and rationalized by the participants—that is, though the examples they provide are produced through the intersection of multiple vectors that they often explicitly acknowledge, ultimately, through their metapragmatic discourse, intersectionality ends up being simplified and pared down (#LoveYourIdentity), so that it becomes just a case of “good” or “bad” speakers of English rather than an account of how this legitimization is produced through racial, capitalist, and colonial relations.

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ORCID

Katy Highet <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4706-0601>

REFERENCES

- Agha, Asif. 2007. *Language and Social Relations*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511618284>.
- Ahmed, Sara. 2012. *On Being Included: Racism and Diversity in Institutional Life*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press.
- Annamalai, E. 2005. “Nation-Building in a Globalised World: Language Choice and Education in India.” In *Decolonisation, Globalisation: Language-in-Education Policy and Practice*, edited by Peter W. Martin, 20–37. Clevedon, UK: Multilingual Matters.
- Assundani. 2020. *The Rawknee featured in the 300 most influential people in Asia 2020 list*. <https://www.sportskeeda.com/gta/rawknee-featured-300-influential-people-asia-2020-list>
- Babcock, Joshua. 2022. “Postracial Policing, ‘Mother Tongue’ Sourcing, and Images of Singlish Standard.” *Journal of Linguistic Anthropology* 32 (2): 326–44. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jola.12354>.
- Bakhtin, Mikhail. 1981. *The Dialogic Imagination*. Austin: University of Texas Press.
- Banerjee-Dube, Ishita. 2014. “Caste, Race and Difference: The Limits of Knowledge and Resistance.” *Current Sociology* 62 (4): 512–30. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011392114524508>.
- Bauman, Richard, and Briggs, Charles L. 2003. *Voices of Modernity: Language Ideologies and the Politics of Inequality*. Studies in the Social and Cultural Foundations of Language, no. 21. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511486647>.
- Blommaert, Jan. 2005. *Discourse. A Critical Introduction*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.

- Carlan, Hannah. 2018. "In the Mouth of an Aborigine": Language Ideologies and Logics of Racialization in the Linguistic Survey of India." *International Journal of the Sociology of Language* 2018 (252): 97–123. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijsl-2018-0016>.
- Chand, Vineeta. 2009. "[V]at Is Going On? Local and Global Ideologies about Indian English." *Language in Society* 38 (4): 393. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0047404509990200>.
- Chun, Elaine W. 2004. "Ideologies of Legitimate Mockery: Margaret Cho's Revoicings of Mock Asian." *Pragmatics: Quarterly Publication of the International Pragmatics Association* 14 (2–3): 263–89. <https://doi.org/10.1075/prag.14.2-3.10chu>.
- Chun, Elaine W. 2009. "Speaking Like Asian Immigrants: Intersections of Accommodation and Mocking at a U.S. High School." *Pragmatics: Quarterly Publication of the International Pragmatics Association* 19 (1): 17–38. <https://doi.org/10.1075/prag.19.1.02chu>.
- Cushing, Ian. 2021. "Say It Like the Queen": The Standard Language Ideology and Language Policy Making in English Primary Schools." *Language, Culture and Curriculum* 34 (3): 321–36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908318.2020.1840578>.
- Duchêne, Alexandre, and Michelle Daveluy. 2015. "Présentation: spéculations langagières: négociier des ressources aux valeurs fluctuantes." *Anthropologie et sociétés* 39 (3): 9–27. <https://doi.org/10.7202/1034757ar>.
- Duchêne, Alexandre, and Philippe N. Humbert. 2018. "Surveying Languages: The Art of Governing Speakers with Numbers." *International Journal of the Sociology of Language* 2018 (252): 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijsl-2018-0012>.
- Evans, Stephen. 2002. "Macaulay's Minute Revisited: Colonial Language Policy in Nineteenth-Century India." *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development* 23 (4): 260–81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01434630208666469>.
- Fanon, Frantz. 2008. *Black Skin, White Masks*. Translated by Richard Philcox. Rev. ed. New York: Grove Press.
- Fernandes, Leela. 2006. *India's New Middle Class: Democratic Politics in an Era of Economic Reform*. Minneapolis, MN: University of Minnesota Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5749/j.ctttsjgt>.
- Flores, Nelson, and Jonathan Rosa. 2015. "Undoing Appropriateness: Raciolinguistic Ideologies and Language Diversity in Education." *Harvard Educational Review* 85 (2): 149–71, 300–1.
- Foucault, Michel. 1991. "Governmentality." In *The Foucault Effect: Studies in Governmentality*, edited by Graham Burchell, Colin Gordon, and Peter Miller, 87–104. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Hall, Kira. 2019. "Middle Class Timelines: Ethnic Humor and Sexual Modernity in Delhi." *Language in Society* 48 (4): 491–517. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0047404519000435>.
- Highet, Katy. 2021. *Becoming English Speakers: A Critical Sociolinguistic Ethnography of English, Inequality, and Social Mobility in Delhi*. PhD diss., UCL Institute of Education.
- Highet, Katy. 2022. "She Will Control My Son": Navigating Womanhood, English and Social Mobility in India." *Journal of Sociolinguistics*. 26 (5): 648–65. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josl.12567>.
- Highet, Katy, and Alfonso Del Percio. 2021a. "Hard Work, Growth Mindset, Fluent English: Navigating Neoliberal Logics." In *The Impacts of Neoliberal Discourse and Language in Education*, edited by Mitja Sardoč, 100–19. New York: Routledge.
- Highet, Katy, and Alfonso Del Percio. 2021b. "When Linguistic Capital Isn't Enough: Personality Development and English Speakerhood as Capital in India." In *The Commodification of Language*, edited by John E. Petrovic and Bedrettin Yazan, 127–43. London: Routledge.
- Hill, Jane H. 1998. "Language, Race, and White Public Space." *American Anthropologist* 100 (3): 680–89.
- Hill, Jane H. 2005. "Intertextuality as Source and Evidence for Indirect Indexical Meanings." *Journal of Linguistic Anthropology* 15 (1): 113–24. <https://doi.org/10.1525/jlin.2005.15.1.113>.
- Hill Collins, P. and Bilge, S. 2020. *Intersectionality*. Second edition. Cambridge, UK; Medford, MA: Polity Press.
- Jaworski, Adam, Nicholas Coupland, and Dariusz Galasiński. 2004. *Metalanguage: Social and Ideological Perspectives*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Kachru, Braj. B. 1985. "Standards, Codification and Sociolinguistic Realism: The English Language in the Outer Circle." In *English in the World: Teaching and Learning the Language and Literatures*, edited by Randolph Quirk, H. G. Widdowson, Yolande Cantù, and British Council, 11–30. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press for the British Council.
- Karjalainen, Reeta. 2018. "'RIP English!': Language Ideological Debate in a Comment Field of a Finnish Entertainment Site." *JYX Digital Repository*. <https://jyx.jyu.fi/handle/123456789/60272>.
- Kohli, Rita, and Daniel G. Solórzano. 2012. "Teachers, Please Learn Our Names! Racial Microaggressions and the K–12 Classroom." *Race Ethnicity and Education* 15 (4): 441–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13613324.2012.674026>.
- Kubota, Ryuko. 2015. "Inequalities of Englishes, English Speakers, and Languages: A Critical Perspective on Pluralist Approaches to English." In *Unequal Englishes: The Politics of Englishes Today*, edited by Ruanni Tupas, 21–42. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- LaDousa, C. 2014. *Hindi is our ground, English is our sky: education, language, and social class in contemporary India*. New York: Berghahn Books.

- LaDousa, Chaise, and Christina P. Davis. 2022. "South Asian Language Practices: Mother Tongue, Medium, and Media." *Annual Review of Anthropology* 51: 289–305. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anthro-041420-110048>.
- LaDousa, Chaise, Christina P. Davis, and Nishaant Choksi. 2022. "Postcolonial Language Ideologies: Indian Students Reflect on Mother Tongue and English." *Journal of Linguistic Anthropology*. Preprint. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jola.12378>.
- Lippi-Green, Rosina. 1997. *English with an Accent: Language, Ideology, and Discrimination in the United States*. London: Routledge.
- Milroy, James. 2001. "Language Ideologies and the Consequences of Standardization." *Journal of Sociolinguistics* 5 (4): 530–55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9481.00163>.
- Nakassis, Constantine V., and E. Annamalai. 2020. "Linguistic Diversity in South Asia, Reconsidered." In *The International Encyclopedia of Linguistic Anthropology*, edited by J. Stanlaw, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118786093.iela0237>.
- O'Regan, John P. 2014. "English as a Lingua Franca: An Immanent Critique." *Applied Linguistics* 35 (5): 533–52.
- O'Regan, John P. 2021. *Global English and Political Economy: An Immanent Critique*. 1st ed. London: Routledge.
- Park, Joseph Sung-Yul. 2009. *The Local Construction of a Global Language: Ideologies of English in South Korea*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter.
- Park, Joseph Sung-Yul. 2021. In *Pursuit of English: Language and Subjectivity in Neoliberal South Korea*. Oxford Studies in Sociolinguistics. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Park, J.S.-Y. and Wee, L. 2009 'The Three Circles Redux: A Market-Theoretic Perspective on World Englishes', *Applied Linguistics*, 30 (3): 389–406. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amp008>.
- Pennycook, Alastair. 1998. *English and the Discourses of Colonialism*. New York: Routledge.
- Proctor, Lavanya Murali. 2015. "English and Globalization in India: The Fractal Nature of Discourse." *Journal of Linguistic Anthropology* 24 (3): 294–314. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jola.12056>.
- Rajagopalan, Kanavillil. 2010. "The Soft Ideological Underbelly of the Notion of Intelligibility in Discussions about 'World Englishes.'" *Applied Linguistics* 31 (3): 465–70. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amq014>.
- Ramanathan, Vaidehi. 2015. "Contesting the Raj's 'Divide and Rule' Policies: Linguistic Apartheid, Unequal Englishes, and the Postcolonial Framework." In *Unequal Englishes: The Politics of Englishes Today*, edited by Ruanni Tupas, 203–21. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Ramjattan, Vijay A. 2022. "Accenting Racism in Labour Migration." *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics* 42: 87–92. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190521000143>.
- Rampton, Ben. 2009. "Interaction Ritual and Not Just Artful Performance in Crossing and Stylization." *Language in Society* 38 (2): 149–76.
- Reyes, Angela. 2017. "Inventing Postcolonial Elites: Race, Language, Mix, Excess." *Journal of Linguistic Anthropology* 27 (2): 210–31. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jola.12156>.
- Rosa, Jonathan. 2016. "Standardization, Racialization, Languagelessness: Raciolinguistic Ideologies across Communicative Contexts." *Journal of Linguistic Anthropology* 26 (2): 162–83. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jola.12116>.
- Rosa, Jonathan, and Nelson Flores. 2017. "Unsettling Race and Language: Toward a Raciolinguistic Perspective." *Language in Society* 46 (5): 621–47. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0047404517000562>.
- Roy, S. 2015. 'Pedagogic Predicament: The Problems of Teaching English within a Postcolonial Space', *Interventions*, 17 (4): 519–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369801X.2014.950316>.
- Sandhu, Priti. 2015. "Stylizing Voices, Stances, and Identities Related to Medium of Education in India." *Multilingua: Journal of Cross-Cultural and Interlanguage Communication* 34 (2): 211–35.
- Saraceni, Mario. 2015. *World Englishes: A Critical Analysis*. London: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Shankar, Shalini. 2008. "Speaking Like a Model Minority: 'FOB' Styles, Gender, and Racial Meanings among Desi Teens in Silicon Valley." *Journal of Linguistic Anthropology* 18 (2): 268–89.
- Silverstein, Michael. 1996. "Monoglot 'Standard' in America: Standardization and Metaphors of Linguistic Hegemony." In *The Matrix of Language: Contemporary Linguistic Anthropology*, edited by Donald Lawrence Brenneis and Ronald K. S. Macaulay, 284–306. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.
- Sium, Aman. 2011. "My Name Is 'Mohamed,' But Please Call Me 'John': Canadian Racism, Spirit Injury and the Renaming of the Indigenous Body as a Right of Passage." In *Spirituality, Education, and Society*, edited by Njoki N. Wane, Energy L. Manyimo, and Eric J. Ritskes, 139–56. Leiden, the Netherlands: Brill. <https://brill.com/view/book/edcoll/9789460916038/BP000011.xml>.
- Spilioti, Tereza. 2020. "The Weirding of English, Trans-Scripting, and Humour in Digital Communication." *World Englishes* 39 (1): 106–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/weng.12450>.
- Tabiola, Honey B., and Beatriz Lorente. 2017. "Neoliberalism in ELT Aid: Interrogating a USAID ELT Project in Southern Philippines." In *Language, Education and Neoliberalism: Critical Studies in Sociolinguistics*, edited by Mi-Cha Flubacher and Alfonso Del Percio, 66–73. Critical Language and Literacy Studies 23. Bristol, UK: Multilingual Matters.

- Tebaldi, Catherine. 2020a. "#JeSuisSirCornflakes': Racialization and Resemiotization in French Nationalist Twitter." *International Journal of the Sociology of Language* 2020 (265): 9–32. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijsl-2020-2101>.
- Tebaldi, Catherine. 2020b. "Bad Hombres,' Aloha Snackbar,' and 'Le Cuck': Mock Translanguaging and the Production of Whiteness." In *Translinguistics: Negotiating Innovation and Ordinarity*, edited by Jerry Won Lee and Sender Dovchin, 206–16. Abingdon, UK: Routledge.
- Thurlow, Crispin. 2006. "From Statistical Panic to Moral Panic: The Metadiscursive Construction and Popular Exaggeration of New Media Language in the Print Media." *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication* 11 (3): 667–701. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2006.00031.x>.
- Tupas, Ruanni. 2022. "The Coloniality of Native Speakerism." *Asian Englishes* 24 (2): 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13488678.2022.2056797>.
- Tupas, Ruanni, and Rani Rubdy. 2015. "Introduction: From World Englishes to Unequal Englishes." In *Unequal Englishes*, edited by Ruanni Tupas, 1–17. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137461223_1.
- Udupa, Sahana. 2018. "Gaal Cultures: The Politics of Abusive Exchange on Social Media." *New Media & Society* 20 (4): 1506–22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444817698776>.
- Urciuoli, Bonnie. 2013. *Exposing Prejudice: Puerto Rican Experiences of Language, Race, and Class*. Long Grove, IL: Waveland Press.
- Vigouroux, Cécile B. 2017. "The Discursive Pathway of Two Centuries of Raciolinguistic Stereotyping: Africans as Incapable of Speaking French." *Language in Society* 46 (1): 5–21. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0047404516000804>.
- Woolard, Kathryn Ann. 1998. "Introduction: Language Ideology as a Field of Inquiry." In *Language Ideologies: Practice and Theory*, edited by Paul V. Kroskrity, Bambi B. Schieffelin, and Kathryn Ann Woolard, 3–47. Oxford Studies in Anthropological Linguistics, no. 16. New York: Oxford University Press.

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